

Pathologist Reasoning-Guided Report Generation

Challenge: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Pathologist Reasoning-Guided Report Generation Challenge

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

REG²

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Pathology examination serves as the final confirmation and gold standard in diagnosis, playing a pivotal role in clinical decision-making. Generating accurate pathology reports is therefore both essential and challenging: pathologists must synthesize vast whole slide images while identifying clinically significant fine-grained features—a cognitively demanding process. Recent vision-language model advances have nonetheless achieved impressive results in automated report generation despite gigapixel-scale image complexity. Our previous challenge, REG2025, benchmarked report generation accuracy, with finalists achieving satisfactory performance. REG2025 benchmark relied on surface-level lexical (via ROUGE-L and BLEU-4) and shallow semantic metrics (SciSpacy and OpenBioLLM), which inadequately captured clinical correctness, negation, numeric fidelity, and omission of safety-critical findings.

In REG², we aim to integrate the diagnostic reasoning process into the conventional report generation based on the success of REG2025. The diagnostic reasoning process constitutes the iterative process by which pathologists explore and evaluate findings to distinguish candidate diagnoses and select reportable features, underpinning both diagnostic accuracy and clinical explainability. This perspective aligns naturally with agentic AI, where reasoning is instantiated as goal-directed task decomposition and workflow design. A broad range of agentic AI methods and frameworks has emerged, demonstrating strong capabilities in planning, tool use, and multi-step decision-making. However, evaluation datasets in the medical domain remain scarce.

Consequently, we introduce this challenge to bridge this gap through three core objectives: (1) constructing a structured chain-of-thought (CoT) dataset that emulates pathologist reasoning pathways, thereby enriching existing WSI-report pairs; (2) proposing novel evaluation metrics capable of quantifying the reasoning performance of models trained on this augmented dataset; (3) Propose an agentic framework for pathology

report generation that explicitly models diagnostic reasoning as task decomposition, planning, and evidence selection; and (4) Benchmark representative agentic and non-agentic baselines to quantify gains in diagnostic accuracy and clinical interpretability.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Report Generation, Multi-modal, Computational Pathology, Agentic AI, Emulating Pathologist, Reasoning

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

When compared with the REG2025 challenge iteration, this year we focus on 4 novel objectives:

1. Construct a structured chain-of-thought (CoT) dataset that emulate pathologist reasoning pathways. This integrated reasoning with conventional report generation provides the foundation for both diagnostic accuracy and clinical explainability.
2. Propose novel evaluation metrics capable of quantifying the reasoning performance of models trained on this augmented dataset.
3. Propose an agentic framework for pathology report generation that explicitly models diagnostic reasoning as task decomposition, planning, and evidence selection.
4. Benchmark representative agentic and non-agentic baselines to quantify gains in diagnostic accuracy and clinical interpretability.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

Input: Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E;) stained pathology slide images (WSIs)

Output: Automatically generated pathology reports guided with pathologist reasoning.

Task Objectives:

- 1) Evaluate the quality of the diagnostic reasoning of algorithms
- 2) Develop generalized medical AI models capable of handling diverse organ specimens from multiethnic populations.

Application Scenarios:

The reasoning-guided pathology report generation developed in this challenge can be applied in various clinical and research settings

- 1) Clinical Decision Support (CDS): Enable pathological reasoning-based screening to support pathologists' practice
- 2) Medical Education: Provide educational tools for teaching diagnostic processes to medical students or residents
- 3) Integration to Pathological AI or Multimodal Medical AI
- 4) Research Benchmark for Computational Pathology

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

MICCAI-ESDIP-ASDP COMPAYL++ workshop
ASDP-ESDIP Tutorial on computational pathology

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

Our previous challenge, REG2025, ran for 16 weeks on the Grand Challenge platform and attracted 389 participants from 40 countries, with 24 teams submitting final solutions. Participants came from diverse backgrounds including universities, hospitals, and medical AI industry, demonstrating broad interest across academic, clinical, and industrial sectors.

REG² extends the previous year's objectives by integrating reasoning components, which is anticipated to broaden the participant base further. Given the utilization of an identical online platform, geographic accessibility constraints are expected to remain minimal.

Consequently, we conservatively estimate 300 to 400 participants for REG².

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

[Revised]

We intend to coordinate 2 specific publication plans for REG².

Plan 1:

Coordination of the REG² proceedings as part of the MICCAI Satellite Event proceedings, allowing our participants to publish their methods in the associated MICCAI Satellite Event Springer LNCS proceedings.

Plan 2:

We plan to publish a post-conference meta-analysis journal manuscript in Medical Image Analysis (MedIA) that will summarize the results, findings, and insights of the 2026 REG challenge. Leveraging the strong visibility of MICCAI and its Satellite Event proceedings, the MedIA paper will offer a more comprehensive account of the task design, evaluation protocols, and lessons learned, helping increase the benchmark's reach and long-term impact.

All organizers will be listed as authors. The primary authorship will be assigned to the 2 or 3 individuals who made the most substantial overall contributions, and the corresponding authorship will be assigned to the primary contact person of the challenge. Top-performing participating teams will be included as co-authors in the resulting challenge publication.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

Yes

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team ([miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de](mailto:micca-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de)) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Hardware requirements for the in-person meeting: 1 projector, 2 microphones, loudspeakers

The REG² Challenge describes an off-site challenge, where 1) during the training phase, algorithms are trained using the participants' computing infrastructure, and 2) during the validation and final testing/ranking phase using the organizers' infrastructure in the platform we will end up using (Grand-challenge.org).

TASK 1: Pathologist Reasoning-Guided Report Generation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

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Consequently, we introduce this challenge to bridge this gap through three core objectives: (1) constructing a structured chain-of-thought (CoT) dataset that emulates pathologist reasoning pathways, thereby enriching existing WSI-report pairs; (2) proposing novel evaluation metrics capable of quantifying the reasoning performance of models trained on this augmented dataset; (3) Propose an agentic framework for pathology report generation that explicitly models diagnostic reasoning as task decomposition, planning, and evidence selection; and (4) Benchmark representative agentic and non-agentic baselines to quantify gains in diagnostic accuracy and clinical interpretability.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Pathology, ASDP, ESDIP, MICCAI

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Euseop Song (Korea University, Korea)
 Han Li (Technical University of Munich, Germany)
 Spyridon Bakas (Indiana University School of Medicine, IN, United States)
 Haasha Bin Atif (Orydex, Pakistan)
 Muhammad Aamir Gulzar (National University of Computer and Emerging Sciences, Pakistan)
 Dewan Bappy (Korea University, Korea)
 Ayako Ura (Juntendo University, Japan)
 Jingsong Liu (Technical University of Munich, Germany)
 Andrey Bychlov (Kameda Medical Center, Japan)
 Junya Fukuoka (Kameda Medical Center, Japan)
 Rajiv Kumar Kaushal (Tata Memorial Hospital, India)
 Ayushi Sahay (Tata Memorial Hospital, India)
 Rajni Yadav (All India Institute Of Medical Sciences Delhi, India)
 Sulen Sarioglu (Memorial Healthcare Group Istanbul, Turkey)
 Serdar Balci (Memorial Healthcare Group Istanbul, Turkey)
 İlknur Türkmen (Memorial Healthcare Group Istanbul, Turkey)
 Yuri Tolkach (University Clinic of Cologne, Germany)
 Norman Zerbe (Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Germany)
 Nadieh Khalili (Radboud University, Netherlands)
 Jang-Hwan Choi (Ewha Womans University, Korea)
 Peter Schüffler (Technical University of Munich, Germany)
 Mohsin Bilal (Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University, Saudi Arabia)
 Sangjeong Ahn (Korea University, Korea)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Sangeong Ahn (Korea University, Korea)
 Email id: vanitasahn@gmail.com

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes, Roles include 1) ensuring and increasing clinical relevance, 2) generation of annotations, 3) review of reference standard, 4) interpretation of results.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI-ESDIP-ASDP COMPAYL++ workshop
ASDP-ESDIP Tutorial on computational pathology

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

N/A

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

miccaireg2026.grand-challenge.org

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Publicly available data is allowed but private annotations of such data is prohibited.

All participants are allowed to use publicly available pre-trained models (e.g., foundation models), as well as additional data from datasets publicly available at the time of the challenge launch.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We will provide Certificates of Merit to the top 3 performing teams.

The challenge organizers are in communication with our societies, industrial partners, and MICCAI SIGs, to sponsor monetary awards for the top 3 teams. Formal confirmation can only be provided after the acceptance of the challenge.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
 - Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.
- A public leaderboard will provide live performance rankings throughout the challenge, while the final leaderboard, reflecting the official results, will be displayed on the platform.
- The top-performing methods (top N) will be publicly announced during the MICCAI 2026 conference.
- All participants will be required to submit a technical abstract detailing their approach, including methodology, results, and key insights.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

[Revised]

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Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Participants are required to submit Docker containers containing their models on the Grand Challenge platform. At the end of the validation phase, participants will be asked to identify which method they wish to evaluate in the final testing/ranking phase. The organizers will then confirm receiving the containerized method and will evaluate

it in the hidden testing data. The participants will be provided guidelines on the form of the container, towards enabling confirmation of reproducibility.

During the training and validation phases, the participants will have the chance to test the functionality of their submission through the online evaluation platform.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We intend to publicly release the training and the validation sets, as soon as the challenge is approved but not later than April 2026, allowing participants to train and tune their methods. The validation data ground truth will not be provided to the participants, but multiple submissions to the online evaluation platform will be allowed for the validation phase. However, only 2 submissions will be allowed in the final testing/ranking data/phase to avoid potential tuning of the submitted approach to the testing data.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration period: From the website launch until the deadline for submitting short papers reporting the method and preliminary results (see timeline below).

1 April 2026 – Registration opens; Training/Validation data released

Registration will open on April 1, 2026. Participants may register via Synapse.org or Grand-Challenge.org (subject to final platform selection) from the launch date until the short paper submission deadline (July 31, 2026). Training data (with ground-truth labels) and validation data (without ground-truth labels) will be made available upon registration.

31 July 2026 – Deadline for short paper and containerized submission

Teams must submit (1) a short paper describing the motivation, related work, method, and results on the training/validation sets, and (2) a containerized implementation of their method. Only teams that submit a valid short paper will have their container evaluated on the hidden test set by the organizers. Final rankings will be determined based on test-set performance, including statistical significance assessment using multiple permutation testing.

7 August 2026 – Initial invitations sent

Organizers will send presentation invitations to teams with a valid short paper submission and a successfully evaluated container. The presentation format (oral vs. poster) will be finalized within the following two weeks.

14 August 2026 – Reviews released

Short paper reviews will be made available to the authors.

19 August 2026 – Test-set summary results shared with participants

Each team will receive a summary of their test-set results to incorporate into the camera-ready version of their paper.

21 August 2026 – Camera-ready paper and copyright form deadline

Camera-ready papers and the required copyright forms must be submitted by this date.

24 August 2026 – Oral presentation preparation for top teams

Top-performing teams will be contacted and asked to prepare slides for oral presentations.

1 September 2026 – Proceedings package submitted to MICCAI

Organizers will submit the complete proceedings materials to the MICCAI 2026 Satellite Events committee for inclusion in the MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings.

4–8 October 2026 – MICCAI 2026 Challenge event

The challenge session will take place during MICCAI 2026 (October 4–8, 2026), including the announcement of the final Top-3 ranked teams.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The Medical Ethics Committee of Korea University Anam Hospital (Korea), Kameda Medical Center (Japan), University Hospital Cologne (Germany), Tata Memorial Hospital (India), All India Institute of Medical Sciences Delhi (India), Memorial Healthcare Group Istanbul (Turkey), and Technical University of Munich (Germany) were approved

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation will be automatically performed in the challenge platform. Information about the evaluation formula and its algorithm will also be available on the platform.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The participants are required to submit their containerized algorithm, during or after the validation phase. Specific instructions for the containerization will be provided after the challenge approval. All challenge participants will be required to accept an agreement through the challenge website that participation in the testing phase of the challenge, will automatically mean that we can make their containerized method publicly available through our challenge webpage and a collective toolkit that we will be putting together.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

There are no conflicts of interest. The only sponsorship for the challenge will be in the form of award money, although the sponsors have not yet been finalized. Access to the test case WSIs and labels, both during and after the challenge, will be restricted exclusively to members of the organizing team.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training

- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Screening

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Report Generation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of patients undergoing invasive procedure (c.f. biopsy or small-sized tissue removal, resection) from multiple organs, including the lung, colon, breast, urinary bladder, stomach, uterine cervix, prostate, and others.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort would be acquired the same way as the target cohort.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Hematoxylin-eosin (HE) stained histopathology whole-slide images

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

For each image in the training data, an anonymous case ID is provided, along with pathology report (including organ, main diagnosis, and required description based on CAP guideline) and structured CoT data (composed of the tuples, containing structured pathologic question, its corresponding answer, and the following question). Pathology report and CoT data will not be provided for test data.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No further information given

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data consists of WSIs from the target cohort, obtained from the organizer center, with following more than 43 diagnostic categories across 8 organs:

- Lung: Adenocarcinoma, Squamous cell carcinoma, Small cell carcinoma, Necrotizing granulomatous inflammation, Normal lung parenchyme, and etc.
- Colon: Adenocarcinoma, Tubular adenoma with low grade dysplasia, Tubular adenoma with high grade dysplasia, Tubulovillous adenoma with low grade dysplasia, Tubulovillous adenoma with high grade dysplasia, Villous adenoma with low grade dysplasia, Villous adenoma with high grade dysplasia, Hyperplastic polyp, Serrated lesion, Normal, and etc.
- Breast: Invasive ductal carcinoma, Invasive lobular carcinoma, Ductal carcinoma in situ, Fibroepithelial tumor, No evidence of tumor, and etc.
- Urinary bladder: Invasive urothelial carcinoma with muscle proper invasion, Invasive urothelial carcinoma with subepithelial connective tissue invasion, Non-invasive papillary urothelial carcinoma (high grade), Non-invasive papillary urothelial carcinoma (low grade), Urothelial carcinoma in situ, and etc
- Stomach: Adenocarcinoma, Tubular adenoma with low grade dysplasia, Tubular adenoma with high grade dysplasia, MALtoma, Normal, and etc
- Uterine cervix: LSIL, HSIL, Squamous cell carcinoma, Adenocarcinoma in situ, Adenocarcinoma, Normal, and etc.
- Prostate: Acinar adenocarcinoma, Normal, and etc.
- Uterine corpus: Endometrial carcinoma, Endometrial hyperplasia, Acute and chronic endometritis, Endometrial polyps, Normal, and etc.

The data provided by Korea University Anam Hospital (Korea), Kameda Medical Center (Japan), and Tata Memorial Hospital (India) includes all the mentioned organs except uterine corpus, whereas the data from other institutions does not include certain organs.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Algorithms should aim to generate comprehensive pathology reports directly from WSIs, guided by pathologists' diagnostic pathways. The target of these algorithms includes accurately identifying and characterizing pathological features such as, tumors, dysplastic lesions, or inflammatory processes across various organs (e.g. lung, colon, breast, urinary bladder), organizing these findings into structured diagnostic reports, and explaining the reasoning process leading to diagnostic conclusions in stepwise manners.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Find algorithm/agent AI model demonstrating high-quality diagnostic reasoning through efficient subtask planning and accurate execution, prioritizing (1) strict reasoning-path correctness and completeness, (2) partial structural agreement with the reference reasoning, and (3) semantic clinical accuracy of edge-level answers.

Corresponding metrics: Binary Path Validity (Validity/Correctness), Edge-F1 Score (Correctness/Robustness of reasoning structure), and Mean Edge Semantic Similarity (MESS) using biomedical embeddings (Accuracy/Consistency of clinical content) The evaluation metrics are subject to further refinement as the task design evolves.

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Data would be collected from organizing centers and scanned using multiple scanners: Aperio AT2, Philips IntelliSite Pathology Solution, and Hamamatsu NanoZoomer

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The slides were scanned at 20X or 40X magnification.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The data would be acquired from seven medical centers across Asia and Europe:

- Korea University Anam Hospital (Korea)
- Kameda Medical Center (Japan)
- Tata Memorial Hospital (India)
- All India Institute Of Medical Sciences Delhi (India)
- Memorial Healthcare Group Istanbul (Turkey)

- University Hospital Cologne (Germany).
- Technical University Munich Hospital (Germany)

Additional medical centers may be included to further improve dataset diversity

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

None

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

In both training and test sets, each case is composed of a single WSI. Training cases include paired pathology reports and CoT data, whereas test cases contain only the WSI.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Total: approximately 15,000 cases

Training: approximately 11,000 cases (paired WSIs, CoT data, and pathology reports)

Validation: approximately 2,000 cases (paired WSIs, CoT data, and pathology reports)

Test: approximately 2,000 cases (WSIs only)

Additional cases can be added to facilitate stable and effective challenge management.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All data have been annotated, and CoT data will be constructed by structured methods based on domain knowledge.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Based on availability

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The distribution of organs and major diagnostic categories will be balanced across training, validation, and test phases. However, institutions, minor/rare diagnostic categories, and novel diagnostic categories may be intentionally distributed unevenly across specific phases to evaluate model robustness and generalization performance.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Pathologists from the data-providing centers provided the original pathology reports for each case, and expert pathologists at Korea University Anam Hospital curated all training and test datasets. The paired CoT data consists of question-answer pairs that simulate the diagnostic workflow of pathologists. These structured questions were constructed from keywords selected through review by expert pathologists at Korea University Anam Hospital, with each keyword extracted from reporting guidelines and credible references to ensure reproducibility.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Not applicable.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The pathologist who participated in this study were subspecialized in gastrointestinal pathology (S.A.), pulmonary pathology (J.F.), uropathology (R.K.K), breast pathology (A.S.) and other pathology specialties, with on average 12 years of experience in subspecial pathology.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

During data curation, cases with disagreements regarding the main diagnosis or grade were resolved through consensus with subspecialist pathologists from the Asian Society of Digital Pathology (ASDP) in each field (e.g., gastrointestinal, urology, pulmonary, breast). The consensus process involved multiple rounds to ensure accuracy and reliability.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Curation of the WSIs and reports were conducted by four pathology trainees and four board-certified pathologists. During curation, cases with poor scan quality, insufficient tissue content, or diagnostically

inadequate specimens were excluded to ensure overall consistency and reliability. Subjective or diagnostically equivocal cases were also removed. Histologic types included in the dataset follow the criteria of the 5th edition of the WHO Classification of Tumours. When original images contained multiple cases, they were manually split into individual cases.

After the curation, the dataset was anonymized and down-sampled to 20x magnification, to ensure consistency, as the original images contained mixed magnifications of 20x and 40x. During anonymization, associated images (e.g., slide labels, thumbnails, etc.) were removed. Final images were stored as TIFF files with standardized file names.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Inter-observer variability among expert pathologists may result in discrepancies in tumor classification and grading. The training and test cases were exclusively curated from cases where consensus among pathologists was achieved.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We evaluate algorithm performance using a three-component framework designed to assess structured diagnostic reasoning, minimal visual grounding, and counterfactual logical reasoning in digital pathology. Each case is represented as a directed reasoning graph in which nodes correspond to diagnostic tasks and edges represent task-to-task transitions annotated with predicted clinical answers. The overall evaluation is decomposed into three complementary components:

1. Workflow Reasoning Score (A)
2. Visual Grounding Score (B)
3. Counterfactual Reasoning Score (C)

The final ranking score is computed as a weighted combination of these three components. These three components are intentionally designed to capture complementary aspects of diagnostic intelligence. Workflow Reasoning Score (A) evaluates structural correctness of the diagnostic pathway. However, structural correctness alone is insufficient: a model may reproduce the expected reasoning graph without grounding its conclusions in

visual input or without truly understanding diagnostic dependencies.

Visual Grounding Score (B) and Counterfactual Reasoning Score (C) are therefore introduced to address these limitations. Together, the three components provide a balanced evaluation of structural reasoning, visual alignment, and logical consistency. The exact weights will be determined through preliminary experiments conducted prior to the challenge launch, ensuring they appropriately reflect both quantitative evaluation results and qualitative diagnostic reasoning quality. The following sections describe each component in detail.

(A) Workflow Reasoning Score

Workflow reasoning evaluates whether a model correctly follows the structured diagnostic decision pathway.

The following metrics are used:

- Binary Path Validity: This metric assesses whether the predicted reasoning graph exactly matches the ground-truth reasoning path. A score of 1 is assigned only when all ground-truth transitions are correctly predicted and no additional transitions are introduced; otherwise, the score is 0. This reflects strict diagnostic reasoning correctness.
- Edge-F1 Score: This metric measures partial structural agreement between predicted and ground-truth reasoning graphs using precision and recall over reasoning edges. It provides graded credit when a model correctly predicts part of the reasoning structure but misses or adds some transitions.
- Mean Edge Semantic Similarity (MESS): This metric evaluates the semantic alignment of predicted clinical answers with ground-truth answers at the edge level using biomedical language model embeddings (OpenBioLLM-Llama3-70B)[2]. Missing edges receive zero semantic credit. MESS ensures that predicted diagnostic conclusions are clinically meaningful even when expressed with different wording.

These metrics are adapted and extended from structured reasoning-path evaluation frameworks [1], which emphasize correctness and completeness of multi-step reasoning processes. The representation of diagnostic reasoning as ordered task transitions is conceptually aligned with sequential task-decomposition principles described in SMART-LLM [3].

(B) Visual Grounding Score (Background Sanity Verification)

To ensure that models do not generate diagnostic claims independently of visual input, we introduce a minimal visual grounding component that requires no additional manual annotation.

Regions of interest (ROIs) are automatically generated using unsupervised foreground-background separation (e.g., Otsu thresholding) [4] to identify non-tissue regions. Background ROIs are sampled exclusively from areas classified as non-tissue.

For each claim-ROI pair, the model must determine whether the region provides diagnostic evidence for the claim. Since background regions do not contain histologic structures, the correct response is expected to be `not_informative`.

The Visual Grounding Score is defined as the proportion of background ROIs correctly classified as `not_informative`. This component addresses a limitation of workflow-only evaluation. A model may correctly reproduce the reasoning structure while generating conclusions independently of visual input. By verifying that background regions are correctly identified as non-informative, the Visual Grounding Score ensures that diagnostic claims remain tied to spatial input and prevents hallucinated visual evidence. While minimal in design, this component compensates for the absence of explicit visual verification in structural reasoning metrics..

(C) Counterfactual Reasoning Score

To explicitly evaluate logical reasoning independent of workflow propagation, we introduce counterfactual

diagnostic scenarios derived from established organ-specific grading and classification systems. For each organ included in the challenge, clinically valid hypothetical modifications are defined based on accepted diagnostic guidelines (e.g., changes in tumor pattern, grade, staging attributes, or classification criteria).

In each counterfactual example, one or more key diagnostic attributes are hypothetically altered (for example, introducing a higher-grade tumor pattern or modifying a staging feature), and the model is required to correctly update downstream diagnostic conclusions accordingly. These updates may include changes in overall grade, classification group, staging category, or other dependent diagnostic outputs.

The Counterfactual Reasoning Score measures the accuracy of these updated predictions. Workflow-based evaluation alone may reward models that propagate earlier predictions along predefined pathways without genuinely understanding the underlying diagnostic logic. The Counterfactual Reasoning Score directly addresses this limitation by requiring models to correctly update conclusions under hypothetical attribute changes. This component therefore isolates rule-based logical reasoning and prevents high scores from being achieved through structural answer propagation alone.

By incorporating counterfactual reasoning across multiple organs, the evaluation framework ensures that models demonstrate consistent logical understanding of clinically established grading and classification systems, independent of visual inference or sequential answer propagation.

[1] Nguyen, Minh-Vuong, Linhao Luo, Fatemeh Shiri, Dinh Phung, Yuan-Fang Li, Thuy Vu, and Gholamreza Haffari. "Direct evaluation of chain-of-thought in multi-hop reasoning with knowledge graphs." In Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: ACL 2024, pp. 2862-2883. 2024.

[2] Pal, M. S. A., & Sankarasubbu, M. (2024). OpenBioLLMs: Advancing open-source large language models for healthcare and life sciences. Retrieved from <https://huggingface.co/aaditya/OpenBioLLM-Llama3-70B>.

[3] Kannan, Shyam Sundar, Vishnunandan LN Venkatesh, and Byung-Cheol Min. "Smart-llm: Smart multi-agent robot task planning using large language models." In 2024 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), pp. 12140-12147. IEEE, 2024.

[4] Otsu, N. A threshold selection method from gray-level histograms. IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, 9(1), 62-66.1979.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The evaluation framework is designed to disentangle four critical properties of diagnostic AI systems:

1. Structured diagnostic reasoning consistency, assessed by Binary Path Validity and Edge-F1.
2. Clinical semantic correctness, assessed by MESS.
3. Visual grounding sanity, assessed through background ROI verification.
4. Logical dependency understanding, assessed through counterfactual reasoning.

Binary Path Validity enforces strict correctness of the reasoning pathway, which is essential in pathology where incorrect reasoning transitions may compromise clinical reliability. Edge-F1 provides graded credit for partially correct reasoning, enabling fair comparison across models with varying reasoning completeness. MESS ensures that predicted answers are clinically meaningful and conceptually aligned with expert references.

The visual grounding component serves as a minimal but necessary safeguard against hallucinated evidence, ensuring that diagnostic claims are not produced independently of visual input. The counterfactual component isolates rule-based reasoning and tests understanding of grading logic without requiring additional image annotation.

Together, these components provide a scalable and transparent evaluation framework suitable for large-scale

digital pathology challenges, balancing reasoning correctness, semantic validity, visual sanity checking, and logical consistency.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Ranking of methods will be determined by aggregating team ranks across the selected evaluation metrics. Specifically, we will follow the DELPHI-based recommendations for image analysis validation [1,2], incorporating i) algorithmic ranking, and ii) statistical significance testing. Building upon the approach used in BraTS 2017-2025, the performance will be evaluated based on the relative performance (as an aggregate metric of the ones described above) of each team's model. For this analysis we will divide the test data into multiple non-overlapping subsets, ensuring balanced class representation. The assessment will involve a detailed analysis of each model's performance. We then compute an average rank for each of the subsets across all metrics, and aggregated these average rankings to produce a conclusive overall ranking.

[1] Reinke et al. Understanding metric-related pitfalls in image analysis validation. Nat Methods. 2024 Feb;21(2):182-194.

[2] Maier-Hein et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nat Methods. 2024 Feb;21(2):195-212.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If an algorithm fails to produce a result metric for a specific test case, this metric will be set to its worst possible value.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Based on the maturity of the ranking system used in the BraTS challenges 2017-2025

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

We will leverage the same statistical framework that has been applying to the BraTS 2017-2025 challenges that provides a fair, transparent, and robust evaluation framework building upon two stages: (i) a ranking score generated for each evaluated method, based on case-wise cumulative rankings aggregated across the pre-specified metrics reported above and across unseen hold-out cases, and (ii) a rigorous statistical significance assessment, based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models. Compared to a simplistic ordinal ranking, this two-staged methodology provides a more holistic assessment of model performance, identifying if performance differences between any two models are statistically significant and systematic, or the result of chance on a particular test set.

The article describing in detail the exact method has been accepted and will be released as part of the MICCAI BraTS 2025 Springer LNCS proceedings.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

SD and IQR across test cases – visualized as violin plots in our meta-analysis article and presented at the time of the challenge. Furthermore, we report the mean, standard errors and outliers.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

One-sided test assessment – the methodological details of the test for significance span over 2 pages of the accepted article. Springer informed us that this article should be released within January 2026. To maintain statistical rigor, a correction for multiple comparisons, such as the Bonferroni correction or controlling the False Discovery Rate, will be applied to the p-values before interpretation.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

N/A, as if an algorithm fails to produce a result metric for a specific test case, we set the scores to the worst possible rank for this case.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

The software that we will use will be released as an open-source tool through GitHub together with the release of the MICCAI BraTS 2025 Springer LNCS article in January 2026.

We will provide pointers to the article and the software repository in the challenge website. We would be happy to update the design document once the article is available to include a link to the github repository.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A